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What are the Obstacles to Central Asian Integration?

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INTRODUCTION

In 1904, British geographer, Halford John Mackinder, argued that the 'heartland' of Eurasia (Central Asia) was the key to the global balance of power, the state that would dominate this area would dominate Eurasia then the whole world. His ideas were widely neglected, however since the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991, his ideas have experienced a renaissance in the study of International Relations of Central Asia. The collapse gave birth to five new independent states, blessed with industrial skills, educated populations and some with resources but all with sinked economies (Megoran and Sharapova, 2013).

Historically, these countries had a lot in common apart from Soviet history - Turkic, Iranian and Muslim roots (Megoran and Sharapova, 2013, p.3). The region was once united under 'Turkestan', however, as an outcome of the Soviet legacy and the 'divide and rule' strategy, the region had been split (Haugen, 2003). Since 1991, the republics have sought to establish themselves as independent actors in the regional stage and rather than unifying, they started moving away from each other (Megoran and Sharapova, 2013, p.3). As a result, regional integration has stagnated and the political situation in the region has been understood as a zero-sum game (Collins, 2009).

The lack of development and the rising external threats have indicated that a regional integration is needed to ensure socio-economic progress. At the same time, the zero-sum nature of the region is dangerous as it can cause minor conflicts to escalate into larger ones. In order to have dispute and conflict settlement mechanisms, as well as to improve inter-state diplomatic relations, the republics need to integrate politically and economically (Collins, 2009).

How a region with such a common culture and history could not achieve integration - is a question with many possible answers. The aim of this dissertation is to analyse the political and economic obstacles to Central Asian integration while recognizing that there is a packing order of issues that depend on one another. The first chapter will revolve around the internal politics of Central Asian states. Specifically, it will focus on how the system of patronage in neopatrimonial states affect democratization efforts and how the latter are further prevented by nepotism. The second chapter will discuss the economic obstacles and the main argument will center around the regional economic disparity and neopatrimonial nature of the republics which create differing economic strategies and prevent economic integration. This will also be illustrated through a case study on the issue of water sharing. Finally, the third chapter will analyse the role of outside powers, noting that integrational efforts in the region have also been prevented from an external perspective. In conclusion, I will agree with the realist view that authoritarian states are less likely to cooperate than democracies. I will utilize academic sources to defend my arguments.

CHAPTER 1: Internal Political Obstacles to Regional Integration

Background

The end of the Soviet era brought about high hopes for democratization in the newly formed states. Initial studies on Central Asia anticipated the beginning of a democratic transition in the region (Kukeyeva & Shkapyak, 2013). The independence of Central Asian countries coincided with the triumph of the US in the Cold War and hence, the spread of liberal democracy and capitalism. In the early stages of Central Asian state-building, Western governments and international organisations had committed significant resources to the implementation and establishment of

democratic policies and institutions in the countries (Giffen, Buxton & Earle, 2005). Domestically, there were high expectations within civil societies to see the constitutionalized democratic values of respect for human rights, legislative elections, institution of the presidency, and the supremacy of international law being effectively put into practice. Nevertheless, by the end of the 1990s, it became evident that Central Asian governments were moving backwards. The successful creation of democratic institutions did not assure the application of democracy as the dominating governing principle and remained on the surface (Kukeyeva & Shkapyak, 2013, p.80; Omelicheva, 2015).

By all appearances, it became evident that all five Central Asian nations had evolved to continue their authoritarian tendencies. By the end of the century, all Central Asian governments were involved in systematic and widespread human rights abuses and undertook extreme measures to silence any opposition force. In 1999, the Central Asian governments were listed among “the most repressive in the world” (Freedom House Survey Team, 1999). Together, these trends left no question that authoritarianism was sustained as the dominant political form in the region.

This phenomenon was not unanticipated, the repressive Soviet past that lasted almost a century, the culture of informal politics based on kinship, traditions and religion - opposed to the liberal democratic paradigm, were clear indicators of the region’s predisposition towards authoritarian rule (Collins, 2006). During the Soviet Union, the states were similar in terms of political structures. However, each country subsequently adopted different political paths, democratic *de jure* but repressive *de facto* and to this day, are all considered authoritarian (Abdukadirov, 2009, p.286; Cummings, 2013).

Due to the prevalence of authoritarianism in the region, it can be deduced that the lack of integration efforts is related to their system of governance. According to the realist perspective, authoritarianism is a major

obstacle for inter-state initiatives because in such leaderships, internal control is preeminent and while integration efforts constitute liberalization, the latter is understood as dangerous for regime maintenance (Kubicek, 1997).

After 1991, as the republics sought to establish themselves as significant independent actors in the regional stage, numerous internal actors vied for political power. In some countries this led to instability while in others, suppression of these actors resulted in reinforcing authoritarian regimes for nearly three decades. For example, in Tajikistan this resulted in a Civil War that lasted for 7 years and in Kyrgyzstan, frequent regime changes coupled with violent cross-border incidents, constituted most of the nation's independent history (Pomfret, 2006, p.2; Rezvani, 2013). While in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan, authoritarianism was seeded from the very beginning (Kubicek, 1998). Since Central Asia has always been a multi-ethnic and regionally divided, the end of the Soviet Union was followed with an internal competition for power in the respective states (Collins, 2006). Therefore, it can be argued that authoritarianism was necessary to ensure stability and regime maintenance. However, after three decades of independence, it is evident that authoritarianism was not an 'interim' system that would gradually evolve into a more liberal system. It had rather become a major obstacle for socio-economic development and overall regional integration (Omelicheva, 2015). The continuation of authoritarian rule can be explained through the internal aspects of Central Asian politics and its regionally divided nature which was suppressed through a clientelist system. The latter was emplaced to prevent the rise of other major powers and keep power within the leader's circle. However, this has only advanced authoritarianism which did not help the strengthening of states in terms of state building (Lewis, 2012).

Political Systems of Central Asian Countries (post-1991)

In the early 1990s, Kyrgyzstan started a course of economic liberalisation which was supported by Western organisations (Pomfret, 2006). However, it is evident today that this strategy was rather unsuccessful. The political regime in Kyrgyzstan is designated as a facade democracy where political power is achieved through corrupt practices. As specified by Laruelle (2012), the republic is best classified as a neopatrimonial multi-party system with many internal problems and struggles for dominance by different elite groups based on an opposition between the north and south (Roy, 2000; Collins, 2006). After two revolutions and eight presidents, it is evident that the instability of Kyrgyzstan is caused by a competition between elite groups. Overall, the multitude of hostilities caused by power politics and corruption led to political instability which in turn, hindered economic development and thus, affected the political integrity of the republic (Collins, 2006).

Kazakhstan's approach to state-building proved to be the most affluent in the region. Under its longest serving president, Nursultan Nazarbayev, "Kazakhstan adopted a Western development model, embracing elements of a democratic order, a market economy, the rule of law, and civil rights" (Pomfret, 2006, p.3). Today, Kazakhstan is at the forefront of Central Asian politics, mostly because of its close ties with Russia and is the obvious economic hegemon of the region. Its economic success is directly related to its abundant oil, gas and uranium reserves which are sold abroad to external partners (Pomfret, 2006). While having liberalized its economy, at present, Kazakhstan remains politically constrained. Laruelle (2012) classifies the leadership of the country as different from traditional autocracies - soft authoritarianism fits the description of the Kazakh regime. This phenomenon is linked to the country's important position in the global energy sector which pushes the state towards maintaining a good political reputation on the surface. Moreover, Kazakhstan

is often under pressure to liberalize as it is an important economic partner to the West. However, the drastic improvement of the population's material well-being along with modernization as a result of economic prosperity overshadows the call for democratization from an external perspective and allows the creation of a false image reflecting Western standards (Pomfret, 2006). Thus, the president is granted covert power to rule arbitrarily through patronage networks and this is further ensured through the removal of all challenges to the leadership (Dave, 2011). In general, for the Kazakh government, economic prosperity has been the pre-eminent objective rather than political change. However, one-sided gains from resource rents have caused socio-economic disparities leading to civil protests¹, indicating that the government's course of actions needs to be revised in order to ensure stability in the future.

Uzbekistan, under its first president, Islam Karimov, undertook a different model based on a strong regime, national consolidation, collective rights and traditionalism which remind of Soviet-style rule. Being the largest country in the region by population and having considerable gas, oil and natural mineral reserves, Uzbekistan is considered to be the fundamental player in the politics of the region. To illustrate, during the Soviet era, its capital city of Tashkent was the centre of Central Asian Soviet politics. Since 1991, Uzbekistan had focused on gradual development and self-sufficiency with the state controlling nearly all aspects of societal life. Therefore, Uzbekistan remained isolationist and was mostly uninterested in joining regional or larger cooperation organizations for most of its modern history. As a consequence, the population did not enjoy the same socio-economic advances as in Kazakhstan. Rents from exports were not distributed to the rest of the society and modernization was not envisioned, forcing people to live under a harsh police regime (Collins, 2006, p.192-198; Pomfret, 2006,

¹ *"The lack of democratic traditions makes the distribution of income from the resource industry non-transparent. This results in a sharp rise in corruption, a huge discrepancy between the incomes of the general population and the elite, and a growing dissatisfaction among the populace"* (Satpayev and Umbetaliyeva, 2015).

p.25-32). Lewis (2012) states that in Uzbekistan, patronage groups consisting of family members and close associates are the main recipients of state wealth. In a regionally divided society such as in Uzbekistan, the system of patronage is viewed as necessary for the sustenance of political stability (Laruelle, 2012). Contrary to other Central Asian societies, in Uzbekistan, patron-client relations are not solely based on dividing gains from state wealth but are further established through assigning different high ranking regional elites that are loyal to the leader, into important positions of authority (Collins, 2006). Nevertheless, the president remained the highest authority in the state for 24 years and cracked down on any opposition to his iron-fist rule, and arguably was able to ensure political stability and security for the Uzbek people at the most basic level. Altogether, the politics of Uzbekistan served as an obstacle to the creation of a politically engaged civil society and drastically slowed down socio-economic development (Pottenger, 2004; Pomfret, 2006).

In both Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, it is obvious that patronage networks along with distribution of rents from exports between the patron and clients constitute a central part of their internal politics and allow for the continuation of the regime. In political terminology, the internal politics of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan are classified by David Lewis (2012) and Laruelle (2012) as neopatrimonial.

Tajikistan had shown glimpses of liberalization efforts after independence (Pomfret, 2006). However, following the civil war that lasted until 1997, authoritarianism had emerged with the arrival of Emomali Rahmon. Similarly to the two countries above, its internal politics are characterized as neopatrimonial (Lewis, 2012).

Patrimonial or neopatrimonial regimes may take extreme forms, as Weber (1978) classified, sultanistic regimes can re-emerge, especially following a long period of traditional and cultural deterioration. Turkmenistan

fits into that category for the obvious reason of having a highly personalist polity that is often linked to the country's oil wealth (Kunysz, 2012; Pomfret, 2006). In a regime where the main source of profit comes from the oil sector, the president wields unlimited power in order to preserve the status-quo of the state. Led by Saparmurat Niyazov, Turkmenistan entered a phase of permanent isolation that is still the country's main foreign policy today. Overall, Turkmenistan is regarded as one of the most repressive countries in the world along with North Korea. With the absence of basic freedom, socio-economic development and citizen's political participation is non-existent and the state holds absolute and uncompetitive power (Kunysz, 2012).

From this classification, it is evident that all of the Central Asian republics are best classified as neopatrimonial regimes and the system of patronage is understood as being essential to their existence and continuity. Predominantly, family members and close associates constitute the main recipients of state wealth, suggesting that there is a trend of nepotism in the region. The latter is an obstacle for regional integration because it reinforces authoritarian rule by facilitating internal control through the system of patronage (Collins, 2009). The next part of this dissertation will attempt to reveal how the nature of informal politics and nepotism is detrimental to regionalism.

Informal Politics and Nepotism

Various strategies are used by Central Asian leaders to assert and maintain power; however, nepotism is deemed to be the most practiced method and is distinctly traditional to autocratic leaderships. This is because in regionally divided societies such as in Central Asia, there is always a perception of danger from other strongholds which explains why nepotism and internal control is viewed as vital for regime maintenance. In general, nepotism allows for the retainment of power within the leader's inner circle

and it served as the basis for the maintenance of the Uzbek and Kazakh regimes, contrasting to only the Kyrgyz experience. Therefore, it is without doubt that nepotism is a major component of Central Asian neopatrimonialism and perhaps culture (Collins, 2006, 2009). All the Central Asian presidents have allowed members of their families and close associates to enjoy the bounties of the patronage system, and this practice is widespread at all levels of power (Laruelle, 2012, p.314). However, in political systems where there are multiple powerful entities and the established patron is not entirely recognized because a leverage in the form of rents from key resources does not exist, nepotism can be the cause of conflict and destabilization, leading to regional security issues such as ethnic conflicts in Kyrgyzstan. In countries possessing important natural resources such as Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, it is observed that autocratic rule is reinforced through the division of state wealth between family members and close associates, and this is threatening to democratic development and regional cooperation. Specifically, because resource rents enable the continuation of patronage networks which create political dynasties (Collins, 2009).

In this section, the cases of nepotism will be analysed within the context of the three Central Asian regimes. Overall, it will focus on how the vitality of internal control in authoritarian countries, informal politics and nepotism reinforce authoritarian rule which prevents democratization and thus, regional cooperation. First, the internal politics of the three countries along with their political economies will be dissected to display how they led to the maintenance of authoritarian rule. Second, the specific cases of nepotism in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan will be presented to reveal how regime maintenance is facilitated and how the presence of key resources serves as a leverage to sustain political authority through patronage networks. The case of Kyrgyzstan will be presented as an exception to the success of the patronage system and nepotism for regime continuity in Central Asia, suggesting that in some rare instances, these trends could be

threatening to regime continuation and overall stability which is not helpful for regional integration. Finally, it will be concluded that political nepotism of Central Asian leaderships is an impeding factor for regional integration and is a lost opportunity for democratization.

The two countries are chosen due to their importance in the region. Uzbekistan is the most populous and Kazakhstan is the most economically advanced in the region. The cases of Tajikistan and Turkmenistan will be omitted since the dissertation is not sufficient for this. However, there is substantial evidence that the presence of patronage systems and nepotism in Tajikistan and Turkmenistan, strengthen authoritarian rule. The works of Kathleen Collins, 'Clan Politics and Regime Transition in Central Asia' (2006) and Eric McGlinchey, 'Chaos, Violence, Dynasty: Politics and Islam in Central Asia' (2011) present reliable evidence and analysis with similar arguments.

Uzbekistan's Regime Maintenance

After gaining independence in 1991, Islam Karimov, a soviet 'aparatchik', came to power by gaining 86% of votes and proceeded by eliminating his opponents who were mostly intellectuals and regional elites. His regime, for most of its existence, was unchallenged and together with his family and inner circle, possessed absolute power over the country. It is true that there were challenges to his reign, however the successful durability of his regime reveals that the leadership maintained a strong grip over the escalation of potential threats (Pottenger, 2004). In the 2000s, many academics often stressed the dangers from other clans in maintaining the regime in Uzbekistan (Fedorov, 2012). Academics such as Kathleen Collins who has written extensively on the topic of clan politics in Central Asia, analysed that the existence of clans in the Uzbek regime "handicaps its power" (Collins, 2006, p.340). In 2006, the former director of the CIA, John Negroponte had stated that "central authority in one or more [Central Asian

states] could evaporate as rival clans or regions vie for power” (Office of the Director of National Intelligence, 2006). True to a certain degree, there were many forewarnings of a possible bad turn of affairs. In the 2005 Andijan crisis where peaceful protestors marched to the streets, the Uzbek authorities ordered the military to shoot at thousands of ordinary citizens. The government stated that it was a terrorist plot, however, there were numerous reports indicating that it could have been an instance of clan struggle (Malashenko, 2012). This suggests that harsh control over internal politics at all costs was the primary concern for the leadership. At the same time, it displays that resistance did in fact exist, however, it was quickly shut down. Throughout Karimov’s rule, opposition parties were eradicated, freedom was tightly controlled and punishments were brutal. Power relations in the country were heavily centralized, leaving no room for political and economic freedoms. Overall, there was not any indication of actual democratic progress or human rights reform (Pannier, 2010). Successful regime maintenance was further facilitated through rents from energy exports which were allocated by the ruling family and close associates - systemized in order to keep power within the president’s inner circle, especially in a historically regionally divided society such as Uzbekistan (Collins, 2009).

Nepotism in Uzbekistan

Following the deadly crisis of 2005, many Western countries condemned and installed sanctions against Uzbekistan. However, Karimov was still able to maximize his authority through Chinese investments in Uzbek energy and mining projects which gave his family full domination over the country. The appointment of his daughter, Gulnara Karimova, to high ranking positions such as representative to the UN office in Geneva and ambassador of Uzbekistan to Spain, further ensured the aforementioned and indicated that a political dynasticism was on its way in Uzbekistan. To illustrate, at the time, she was listed as one of the richest people in Switzerland and owned the Swiss company ‘ZeroMax’ which profited from

the export of Uzbek oil and gas (Pannier, 2010). This reveals that natural resource rents were directly allocated by the ruling family through corrupt practices which facilitated control over internal politics. Considering her appointments to high governmental positions and business links, she was widely considered to be Karimov's successor and was the symbol of nepotism in the impoverished Uzbekistan (Lewis, 2012). Together, all of these emphasize the relationship between nepotism, patronage networks and autocratic regime continuation in Karimov's Uzbekistan. Overall, the harsh dictatorship and fortunes made by his daughter through corrupt allocation of state wealth have only advanced authoritarianism. The undermining of democratization through heavy control of internal politics was an obstacle for regional integration (Collins, 2009).

From the above example, it is evident that this type of leadership leads to states being unable to achieve any kind of political progress and leaves them in stagnation, with only the ruling family and close associates being the beneficiaries. Specifically, economic stagnation pressurizes the state to use coercive force rather than financial persuasion (Lewis, 2012, p.117). Nepotism further facilitates harsh control over internal politics which is perceived as 'necessary' for regime maintenance in regionally divided societies and together this becomes preemptive for successful state building. As a result, cooperation with neighbouring states becomes unfavored because ruling families in autocratic regimes tend to monopolize important economic sectors such as energy and agriculture and impose trade barriers. This is because economic openness is inconvenient for regime maintenance and can be a potential catalyst for the emergence of strong oppositions. Through such methods, regional cooperation is further prevented on an economic level (Collins, 2009, p.255-256).

However, Uzbekistan's example is not distinctive - this trend is evident in all the other Central Asian states as well, implying that the overall pre-eminence of internal control in authoritarian states poses a limit to

economic regionalism. Kazakhstan's case exposes that a Machiavellian type of force is not a necessity to secure the continuation of a regime through internal control. It reveals that economic openness and good socio-economic development neither ensure democratization nor regional cooperativism (Lewis, 2012, p.117).

Kazakhstan's Regime Maintenance

Nursultan Nazarbayev, who rose to power in a similar fashion as his Uzbek counterpart, having descended the throne last year, is still considered by many to be the covert leader of his country. While being authoritarian in designation, Kazakhstan is distinct from Uzbekistan in the fact that good relations with global powers always played a more substantive role in the government's policy. By being accepted by the wider international community to a certain degree, Nazarbayev was able to use export rents to modernize the country while maintaining internal control without having to crack down on opposition in an overt manner. By designating himself as the 'elbashi' (the leader of the nation), Nazarbayev was able to utilize his charisma to rule arbitrarily through covert force which focused on persuasion through discursive efforts rather than coercion and the creation of a facade democracy (Isaacs, 2010, p. 442). This was all made easier by the significant amount of rents earned from energy exports (Schatz & Maltseva, 2012; Lewis, 2012, p.117). Through these, Nazarbayev was able to silence the formation of any major oppositions that could potentially challenge his rule and dynasticism (Laruelle, 2012, p.320). However, the Kazakh authorities did, in fact, use coercive force as last resort in 2011, 16 factory workers from a large crowd of protestors who organized a strike were shot dead. Other than this and few other protests, the leadership was unchallenged. Similarly to Uzbekistan and to a larger extent, regime maintenance was facilitated through rents from energy exports which were mostly allocated by the ruling family and used to gain civil support by advancing socio-economic development.

Nepotism in Kazakhstan

The trend of nepotism is also exceptionally evident in Kazakhstan. The president appointed his son-in-law, Rakhat Aliyev to various high governmental positions such as the first vice foreign minister and ambassador of Kazakhstan to Austria, before removing him for his aspirations to run for presidency and accusing him of murder charges (Lewis, 2012; OHCHR, 2020). His wife, Nazarbayev's daughter, Dariga, who came into the politics scene in the 2000s, was widely viewed as his heiress with her appointment as deputy prime minister of Kazakhstan. Before Nazarbayev's resignation, she was elected as the Chairman of the House which was seen as a move to ensure that power remains within the family. Nazarbayev also appointed his grandsons and other relatives to governmental positions. During his reign, many corruption scandals surfaced to the political arena, the most notorious being the Kazakhgate scandal which revealed multiple offshore accounts with hundreds of millions of dollars linked to Kazakh oil deals with American companies, held by the president and his prime minister (OHCHR, 2020). Through such corrupt and hidden practices, the Kazakh leadership and the ruling family were able to retain public money in their inner circle and use it to magnify their dynastic authority over the country (Laruelle, 2012) . This was further ensured through various attempts to 'persuade' the population by building modern infrastructure and lifting the overall domestic socio-economic situation (Schatz and Maltseva, 2012).

From this, it is obvious that the Kazakh government, being similar to a rentier state, utilized its profits from exports to assert political power and build support. As analysed by Lisa Anderson (1987) and Giacomo Luciani (1990), when external energy resources are the main forms of profit of the state, the latter becomes autonomous from society because the tax burden is reduced and the state is able to use its revenues to 'buy' domestic peace and gain

popular consent, leaving the population depoliticised. In Kazakhstan, this led to the continuation of the autocratic regime through modernization efforts (Franke, Gawrich and Alakbarov, 2009; Hachemaoui, 2012). Simultaneously, since energy exports limit the state to trade more with external partners because of larger demand, inter-regional cooperation in the sphere of energy was stagnated. In turn, these rents were used to accumulate power and nepotism further reinforced this by facilitating control over state resources (Collins, 2009, p.255). Therefore, it is deduced that economic success from the export of key resources along with good socio-economic development does not ensure democratization (Hachemaoui, 2012). On the contrary, the aforementioned can shape an ideal circumstance for authoritarian rule which is a negative factor for regionalism.

Kyrgyzstan's Unsuccessful Regime Maintenance and Nepotism

Kyrgyzstan's example reveals how nepotism can trigger political collapse. It raises questions regarding the success of regime maintenance and stability in neopatrimonialism by demonstrating how the breakdown of patronage networks exposes the weakness of a state affected by decades of informal political decision making. In the beginning of the 1990s, Kyrgyzstan was deemed as the sole 'island of democracy' in the region. However, it quickly became evident that autocratic tendencies proceeded in the country. The first two presidents, Askar Akaev and Kurmanbek Bakiev followed authoritarian patterns for almost two decades and were both overthrown as a result of violent regime changes backed by opposition composed of the country's elites (Rezvani, 2013, p.68). In 2005, President Askar Akaev, a liberal non-communist leader whose family and associates started to control business and politics after 2000, was expelled by competing political forces from the impoverished south of the country who had succeeded in mobilizing widespread resistance to the president following corrupt parliamentary elections. His successor, Kurmanbek Bakiev repeated the same mistakes of the previous leader, costing him his presidency (Collins, 2009, p. 264). His

family started to seize away the commercial and economic resources of competing elites. They started to crack down on NGOs and the media to stifle all dissent, establishing what appeared to be a traditional authoritarian government. However, in the meantime, elites from the north of the country, mobilised a crowd of demonstrators in April 2010 to push Bakiev out of office. Following a period of confrontations and violence, Kyrgyzstan had now attempted a more diverse political structure, with some progress in channeling rivalry amongst competing elites across through the parliamentary system. The democratic transition was evident with the fair election of Atambaev, however, rather than focusing on genuine reforms, he was busy with retaining power and selected president Jeenbekov as his successor, in hopes of keeping power (Temirkulov, 2010). However, this quickly turned into a rivalry between the two, marking a failure of his planned power transition. The current president removed the ex-president's proteges from governmental positions and replaced them with his own close associates including his brothers, indicating that nepotism in Kyrgyzstan has become a trend (Engvall, 2019).

Overall, it is deduced that in Kyrgyzstan, presidents do not last but corruption remains (Engvall, 2019). Different leaders and political elites constantly struggle for power and the absence of state wealth from key resources to serve as a leverage for the sustainment of patronage networks is a dominant reason for political instability in the Kyrgyz republic. The instances of nepotism have led to frequent power shifts and genuine reforms were not achieved. Democratic change is not in the interest of the political elite that constantly seek political power. The armed conflicts that occurred because of instability, corruption and competition between elite groups has created a security dilemma in the region leading to neighbouring countries closing their borders with Kyrgyzstan, further impeding regionalism. The Kyrgyz example also unveils the weakness of Central Asian states which reinforces patronage systems (Lewis, 2012, p.119).

Conclusion

As written by many news sources and analysts on Central Asia, it is obvious that nepotism prevails in these countries and has become a trend. The allocation of state wealth by the leadership and the ruling family allowed for the continuation of the authoritarian regime. In Uzbekistan, many analysts stressed the existence of other challenging clans and anticipated the regime's downfall. However, the absence of any cases of administrative decentralization throughout Uzbekistan's political history proves that the power balance within the country only shifted with the death of the president himself which is a strong indicator of the regime's success. In Kazakhstan, there were no major indicators of challenges to the regime either, the president was able to rule almost freely and left the position with his own will. In both countries, wealth from energy exports were utilized to secure the sustenance of the regime. Therefore, it is deduced that nepotism facilitated the continuation of authoritarian rule. At the same time, the predominant focus on internal political control impeded democratization and thus regional integration. In contrast, the absence of rents from key resources in Kyrgyzstan has hindered regime maintenance and created a competition for power between different elite groups who have attempted to establish their rule through corrupt practices.

CHAPTER 2: Economic Obstacles to Regional Integration

Background

The end of the Soviet Union proved to be disruptive for the new Central Asian countries. The Soviet ruble was impossible to retain as the common currency since it exacerbated hyperinflation and was abandoned in 1993. At this point, the survival of the region's economies was uncertain but was eventually managed through various strategies. The beginning of 2000s marked the transition from central planning towards market-based

economies, and the five countries had started to become more differentiated with the introduction of subsequent national economic plans. After declaring independence, except for Kyrgyzstan, in the other four countries, the First Secretaries appointed by Gorbachev remained in power. Not surprisingly, it was the Kyrgyz republic that became the most liberal regime in the region while Turkmenistan took a distinctly opposite stance as it embraced a cult of personality and focused on strict and minimal economic change. Kazakhstan's economy fell in the hands of the president's inner circle. Uzbekistan remained a tightly controlled political system and its economic reforms were gradual and modest. Tajikistan was in a different category since it did not gain independence peacefully. The Tajik Civil War which lasted from 1992 to 1996, dominated political developments and delayed implementation of economic strategy. In the beginning of the 21st century, the five countries' economic performance started to be visibly different, reflecting policy choices (Pomfret, 2006, p.1-9).

The state-building process unveiled the different courses undertaken by each country which had one commonality - they all opted towards command economic systems. At the start of the decade, Kazakhstan experienced an economic boom as it emerged as a significant oil and gas producer. Its GDP along with living standards were the highest in Central Asia (Pomfret, 2005). Similarly, Turkmenistan was able to export its abundant energy reserves and ameliorate certain economic policies. In both autarkic Uzbekistan and liberal Kyrgyzstan, economic development was less buoyant and compared to Kazakhstan, their living standards were visibly lower. Tajikistan was the worse of all and ranked among the world's poorest nations since the end of the Civil War. Kazakhstan's higher living standards were related to its more diversified economy with a variety of mineral and energy resources. Uzbekistan's economy was dominated by cotton. In terms of resources, Turkmenistan had benefited from the production of naturas and Tajikistan along with Kyrgyzstan lacked key resources. Both Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan began exporting its energy resources. They especially

benefited from the rise of energy prices compared to the Soviet times. Uzbekistan also experienced a cotton boom as prices increased worldwide during the second half of the 1990s (Pomfret, 2006, p.10-21).

As it is evident today, the export of energy resources has been the main catalyst for economic progress in Central Asia which created a power disbalance in the region. This is because energy resources such as oil and gas are inelastic, meaning that demand for it is always existent no matter the change in price - allowing oil exporters to benefit from stable revenues and large demands. Hence why the economies of both Kazakhstan and Turkmenistan have experienced vertical economic growth, whereas Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan have been unable to earn substantially from the export of such resources. Uzbekistan, having both oil and gas reserves along with abundant natural minerals, and a developed cotton industry, has been able to focus on gradual economic development and autarky (Pomfret, 2006, 2019). I hereby make the point that the regional economic disbalance as a result of mismatched experiences along with the neopatrimonial nature of the internal politics, are major factors for the lack of economic and overall cooperation, and a possible catalyst of regional conflicts.

Central Asian Economies in Transition

The Kyrgyz republic, being the most liberal economy in the region, was strongly supported by the IMF and World Bank and in 1998 became the first Central Asian economy to accede to the WTO. However, after 1998, the Kyrgyz economy was badly affected by both the domestic banking crisis and Russian Crisis (Pomfret, 2006). Today, Kyrgyzstan is a lower-middle income country and its economy is one of the poorest in the region. Its GDP ranks at US \$8 billion with a GDP per capita of US \$1,277. The nation has been heavily affected by instability since 1991, mainly because of corruption and nepotism which became causes of civil conflicts and regime changes which amounted into wider, regional instabilities. Its economy mostly relies on the

export of natural minerals and workers remittances (Pomfret, 2019). In order to diversify its struggling economy, the plan to build a hydrocarbon dam has been the cause of regional conflicts which will be explored in the next chapter.

Kazakhstan was viewed as a more liberal state at first and had the highest living standards in the region (Pomfret, 2005). Even though macroeconomic control was slower than in the Kyrgyz republic, Kazakhstan moved fairly quickly with price liberalization and enterprise reform. The Russian Crisis in 1998 hit Kazakhstan the hardest, its currency went through severe devaluation. However, the growth of oil prices after 1999 allowed Kazakhstan's economy to grow rapidly by exporting its resources abroad (Pomfret, 2006). Today, Kazakhstan is an upper-middle-income country with a GDP of US \$181.2 million and a GDP per capita of US \$9,966, both being the highest indicators in the region (World Bank, 2018; IMF, 2018).

Uzbekistan's economy was one of the least liberalized. The government kept harsh control over the economy. Although illiberal, the economy gradually grew since independence. As a result of its strategy, macroeconomic control was achieved slower than both Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. Cotton and wheat were important for the agriculture sector which, up to present time, makes up a significant percentage of its GDP along with gas and gold exports. Uzbekistan has moved cautiously with attempts to establish a market economy. In 1996, heavy exchange control was introduced as cotton prices fell (Pomfret, 2006). This became more relaxed in 2003 and after a long period of isolation, Uzbekistan has started a course of economic liberalization and announced a radical opening from 25 years of having a closed and state-controlled economy (Pomfret, 2019). As of 2019, its GDP is at US \$60.5 million and GDP per capita is at US \$1,831 (IMF, 2019).

Turkmenistan has also been classified as a slow reformer. The first president established a personality cult and adopted populist policies aimed at minimizing fundamental change by turning into permanent isolationism. Initially, a range of free utilities were paid for by natural gas export revenues but it was soon undermined. Instead, revenues from natural resources have been used for prestige projects (Pomfret, 2006). With the arrival of President Berdimuhamedow, the regime's economic policies have not been improved and continue to follow the model of a classic rentier state by relying on hydrocarbon exports as the major source of revenue and its isolationist policy which is a direct obstacle for regionalism (Pomfret, 2019). Today, Turkmenistan is classified as an upper-middle income country and has the world's fourth largest gas reserves. Its GDP sits at US \$40.8 million with a GDP per capita of US \$7,065 (World Bank, 2018).

In Tajikistan, as a result of the civil war, the economy of the country was destroyed. After the end of the war, the political situation remained fragile and the government's authority did not cover the entire national territory. Poor security environment discouraged investment and lack of control deterred economic activity. The government was surviving in the mid 1990s by military loans from Russia and following the civil war, by aid from multilateral financial institutions (Pomfret, 2006). Today, Tajikistan remains the most impoverished nation in the region. It has ameliorated its impoverished situation, however; from 2000 to 2017, the poverty rate fell from 83% to 29.5% of the total population. Nevertheless, the lack of key resources prevents it from achieving significant economic progress (Pomfret, 2019). As of 2018, its GDP equalled US \$7.5 million and GDP per capita is the lowest in the region at US \$822. Similarly to Kyrgyzstan, it relies heavily on worker remittances and the export of minerals (Pomfret, 2019). Its plan to construct a hydrocarbon dam in hopes of diversifying its fragile economy has also caused tensions with neighbours.

Implications for Economic Cooperation

The Central Asian republics emerged from similar economic backgrounds but by the twenty first century, their economic strategies and experiences had become sharply differentiated - a major obstacle for regionalism. This was mostly due to the spatial distribution of natural resources which led to the emergence of different economic strategies and resulted in economic disparities (Pomfret, 2016, 2019). For example, since energy resources are a global necessity, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan gain more from cooperating with major external powers simply because of high demand and outside political support that are needed for regime survival. However, as a result of hindered energy trade in Central Asia, the overall economic development of the region has stagnated and further exploited the already low trade and economic disparity (Cummings, 2013)². Differing national interests can be particularly dangerous for issues such as resource-sharing which will be explored in the next chapter. At the same time, the neopatrimonial nature of the republics further prevented attempts towards economic regionalism. Since political power and wealth accumulation are preeminent for neopatrimonial regimes, such initiatives are deemed as dangerous for regime maintenance (Collins, 2009, p.264). This is because regional economic cooperation is interlinked with trade liberalization which incorporates lower trade tariffs, open economic areas and open borders that cannot be achieved without giving up state control over the economy. Specifically, such liberalization methods cut into the state's wealth from exports (which serves as the basis of patronage systems) and suppress the ability to create monopolies which are of major importance for neopatrimonial states. Moreover, in post-communist countries, it is observed

² *"Tajikistan's exports to Uzbekistan declined from 12.5 per cent in 1993 to 5.3 per cent in 2008 and further down to 4.4 per cent in 2011. Similarly, imports declined from 27.5 per cent to 4.7 per cent and to 2.0 per cent, respectively, during the same periods (National Statistical Committee of Tajikistan, 2014). Inter-ethnic tensions also affect inter-state relations in Central Asia. For example, after the Kyrgyz-Uzbek riots in the South Kyrgyzstan in 2010, the volume of trade between the two declined drastically from US \$285.3 million to US \$208.7 million between 2009 and 2011"* (Felipe and Kumar, 2010)

that there is widespread corruption in customs and border agencies that facilitate illegal trade which are major sources of rents. Tariff liberalisation implies that such agencies ought to be regulated in order to accelerate inter-regional trade. At the same time, liberalising trade and FDI poses a risk for monopolies because of increased competition. From these, it is obvious that regionalism and corruption are juxtaposing notions. Economic integration cuts into the patronage base of the regime and rents that are used to support patronage systems (Collins, 2009, p.256). Therefore, economic integration has been limited in the region. At the same time, the distinct economic experiences have caused regional tensions based on a conflict of interests.

CASE STUDY: The Issue of Water Sharing and its Complications

The sharing of water is perceived by many academics as the predominant factor which further exacerbated the low intra-state trade and overall cooperation. It is evident that there are many other economic factors that would be useful in evaluating the lack of regional integration such as an analysis of each country's economic policies and their effects or corruption in important economic sectors. Many academics such as Richard Pomfret (2006) and Marlen Laruelle (2012) have written extensively on these issues. However, the issue of water sharing is the best case example as it unveils how economic imbalance and opposing interests can be the causes of larger conflicts both on state and local levels. At the same time, it serves as a prism to analyse the political and economic legacies of the Soviet Regime. It also allows the reader to grasp the magnitude of hostilities that were caused by conflicting interests and the overall lack of cooperation on a state level which resulted in an ethnic conflict between two groups from unusually similar backgrounds in 2010 (Pawletta and Gubaidullina, 2015).

As reported by the European External Action Service (EEAS) (2011), water is “one of the most precious resources in [Central Asia] and can be a significant source of tension” (EEAS, 2011). During the Soviet Union, water-sharing in the region was administered by Moscow. The end of the Soviet Union was followed by stagnating economic issues in the region. Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, in particular, suffered the most because of their geographic locations. (Mosello, 2008). Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, thanks to their energy resources, profited from energy exports and were able to supply both Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan with energy supplies. As the two eastern states lack such resources and depend on energy imports from the three neighbouring countries, they have struggled to develop their economies. However, due to their mountainous terrain and water sources, they both have strong hydropower potential. Currently, the two countries are only able to utilize less than 10% percent of their potential. From this, it is understandable that the building of hydrocarbon dams present a vital solution for their economic progress (Pawletta and Gubaidullina, 2015).

The rivers of Syr Darya and Amu Darya originate in the mountains of Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, respectively. Together, they make up the main sources of water in the region as they provide about 90% of the region’s water. As a result, the southern flow countries of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are directly dependent on correct regulation of the rivers. Since 1991, both the Kyrgyz and Tajik republics had plans to construct hydropower plants to profit from the export of electricity. However, this caused diplomatic tensions with Uzbekistan. The transboundary water sharing issue destabilized the Central Asian region, specifically the Ferghana Valley which is located between Tajikistan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan, and resulted in ethnic conflicts based on a competition of water and land (ICG, 2014).

Hydropower plants pose a direct threat to the Uzbek economy. The cotton sector in Uzbekistan is a major source of profit and makes up about 30% of its GDP, and requires constant irrigation. To sustain this, the state utilizes 60% of its own domestic water reserves and to minimize this, it is largely dependent on irrigation from the two rivers (EEAS, 2011). Therefore, plans to build hydropower plants present a direct threat to Uzbekistan's economy as they can drastically decrease the flow of water. At the same time, for both Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, the construction of hydropower plants presents a chance for their struggling economies. As a result of conflicting interests, diplomatic tensions evolved into genuine security issues in the region. At first, the president of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov threatened to use military force if the two countries were to start building the dams (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2018). Then, as Uzbekistan provided energy supplies to the two countries, the president ordered the raising of energy prices and cut off electricity supply lines. In return, Kyrgyzstan blocked off a water canal to Uzbekistan and overall, such 'backward' diplomacy was sustained for sometime. However, as a result of strained relations, clashing economic interests and power politics led to the escalation of more dangerous and dividing issues in the region (International Crisis Group, 2014).

Economic disparities, coupled with competing interests, contributed to more regional destabilisation and ethnic tensions that centered not just on water but also on land in the Ferghana Valley which is one of the most densely populated areas in the region, bordering Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan. The valley is of major economic value to Uzbekistan as it is where its cotton industry is based. However, the valley had been plagued by constant skirmishes and the water-sharing issue further exacerbated hostile relations. This is because the borders in the valley are mostly arbitrary (a legacy from Soviet times) and the three countries have enclaves. As a result of strained relations, the countries struggled to maintain control over the enclaves and frequent skirmishes between local farmers arose at the

borders, causing persistent problems of boundary demarcation and delimitation. Frequent security issues resulted in a major escalation of events: in 2010, in the city of Osh, Kyrgyzstan, more than 400 to a thousand people died as a result of ethnic clashes between Kyrgyzs and Uzbeks. Threatened by hegemonic ambitions of Uzbeks, numerous Kyrgyz mobs who were reportedly supported by President Bakiev, attacked Uzbek civilian populations in the south of the country (International Crisis Group, 2014). This marked the boiling point of tensions which led to a diplomatic 'embargo' in the region. As a result of regional destabilization, transportation and human movement between Uzbekistan and the two countries were completely cut off. The country had built a fence at the Uzbek-Kyrgyz border and installed mines on its Tajik frontier, rendering the situation even more hostile. Uzbekistan brought back the visa-free policy and returned flights to its eastern neighbours only in 2017 with the arrival of President Mirziyoyev. Overall, strained diplomatic relations and conflicts that originated from the issue of water-sharing resulted in major ethnic violence which culminated in the deaths of thousands of human beings.

Even though the present-day situation appears to have eased following the election of Uzbek President Mirziyoyev, who was able to secure the signing of border demarcation agreements and ameliorated border-crossings, the hostile relations that lasted for more than a decade cannot be ignored (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2018). The President's incentive to partly finance the hydroelectric dam projects could partly indicate that the Uzbek authorities are not entirely giving up on the issue and are determined to have veto-power in case the dams will affect irrigation. However, these are all steps in the right direction and are cooperative examples of diplomatic relations. As for the effect of dams on irrigation, substantive impact analysis studies have been carried out by the World Bank and International Crisis Group which reported that the dams should be harmless for Central Asian irrigation (Engineering and Dam Safety Panel of Experts, 2014). Foreshadowing that the realization of the projects

will surely improve the economies of the two countries and the new economic balance in the region could create an ideal circumstance for cooperation.

In conclusion, the reluctance to cooperate led to more damaging diplomatic relations that triggered ethnic tensions in a region where countries share more than a common Soviet past - similar ethnicity, culture, and language. The destabilization of the Ferghana Valley took the lives of thousands of innocent people that became targets for criminals and revealed the risks of aggressive foreign policy that constitutes an obstacle to regional integration.

CHAPTER 3: External Obstacles to Regional Integration

Background

From the above analysis and discussions, it is evident that for Central Asian integration, democratization and economic liberalization are needed. External political and economic obstacles pose a foremost threat for such initiatives. This chapter will focus on Russian and Chinese interests in the region, along with the wider represented regional organizations that Central Asian republics are part of. The first part will focus on Russia's influence in Central Asia and how integrational efforts are put at risk through diplomacy and economic dependence. In the second part, Chinese economic relations with Central Asian countries will be put forward as a counter-argument, indicating that this can rather be helpful for regional integration in the future. Finally, the chapter will conclude with an analysis of how wider represented regional organizations impede integration in Central Asia by entrapping them and leading to the emergence of differing national interests.

Many academics have put forward the idea that a Second Great Game is currently taking place in the region between Russia and China.

Specifically, they have argued that Russia has had less focus on the region which allowed Chinese economic expansion. Moreover, Russia's political and economic regression has been commonly put forward and analysed to explain its declining interest in Central Asia by mainly Western analysts. However, there is evidence that Russia still holds major power in the region and a Second Great Game is also not relevant because Russian and Chinese cooperation has been efficient and preferred by both sides which is evident through their close cooperation in the SCO. In fact, their cooperation in the framework of Central Asia has allowed for this amalgamation - a move to withhold Western influence in the region (Skalamera, 2017).

Russia and Central Asia

Although Russia has been deemed to be on the decline by Western analysts that have focused on the effects of sanctions, it is unforeseeable that Russia will lose out its position in Central Asia to China anytime soon. It is evident that trade between the region and Russia has decreased over the years and China has become the region's major economic partner. However, politically, China has neither the incentive nor the capability to export its brand of realpolitik into Central Asia (Skalamera, 2017). The culture of Russian diplomacy is so far-reaching that there is still a comprehensive symbiosis between Russian and Central Asian leaderships which demonstrates that Central Asia continues to be under the sphere of Russian influence. That said, the Russian-Central Asian bond can be characterized by the prevalence of authoritarianism and economic interdependence.

Decades long of mutual existence under the Soviet Union have secured Russian-Central Asian cooperation with the coming to power of ex-Communist leaders in the newly independent countries. The current leaderships were also once part of the wider Communist party and it is largely observable that they hold Russia as their main foreign partner. Specifically, the culture of Russian diplomacy towards the region is largely

based on the support of the authoritarian regimes of Central Asia. Similar regimes with similar interests are necessary for Russia to ensure strategic cooperation in its fight against the propagation of Western ideology in the post-Soviet space. In Central Asia, just as in post-Soviet Russia, the Western development model has been unsuccessful and Kyrgyzstan's failure to achieve stability by opting for a liberal economy has demonstrated that it is rather unhelpful. The mentioned countries all continue to perceive this model as impractical and believe that a strong regime is key for development (Malashenko, 2013;Skalamera, 2017).

Economic Dependence of Central Asia on Russia

Historically, Russia has been an important economic partner for Central Asia and has been a traditional market for all the Central Asian republics, and is the main regional player. There has also been considerable aid from Western countries towards promoting economic liberalization. At the same time, the region has become a major consumer of Chinese goods (Skalamera, 2017; Mariani, 2013). Therefore, in order to profit from the competition of interests, Central Asian countries adopted a multi-vector foreign policy, including in economic relations (Malashenko, 2013). Russia's importance for the republics lies in the energy trade as most of it is transported through Russian-built pipelines that are mainly directed northwards. Currently, most of Central Asia's infrastructure has been left from Soviet times and transport routes are heavily oriented northwards rather than connecting the five republics with each other which presents an impending factor for interstate cooperation (Kubicek 1997). As a direct result, 70% of Central Asian exports to Europe have to go through Russia, further increasing the region's dependence on its relations with the North (Skalamera, 2017). Therefore, cooperation with Russia is not simply a historically friendly relation, Central Asian economies are considerably dependent on cooperation with Russia, mostly in terms of the export of raw materials and energy. At the same time, the republics benefit from the

access to Russian finances and labor migration, which leads to high remittances flows that countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and to a lesser extent, Uzbekistan are significantly dependent upon (Bobokulov 2006). The Russian economic influence allows it to create political obstacles towards the integration of Central Asia. While on the opposite, Western and Chinese economic support could potentially promote a single Central Asian market (Patnaik, 2019).

Russia's Political Stance

For Russia, it is preeminent to keep its influence in the region as an escalation of Western influence at its Southern border is threatening. Russia's advances in Ukraine and the annexation of Crimea is exemplary and shows the extent of Russia's willingness to maintain control in the post-Soviet space. At the same time, these events have caused concerns in Central Asia, for instance with regard to the future of both Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan's multi-vector foreign policy. Currently, Russia continues to support authoritarian regimes in the region while ensuring that the region is kept as a divided entity. All of the regional cooperation organizations are either initiated by Russia or include the country as a member (Skalamera, 2017). Central Asian integration efforts are seen as part of wider democratization efforts that have been generally supported by Euro-Atlantic organizations. A powerful, democratic and integrated Central Asia would be threatening for Russia as it would most likely invite Western interest (Dubnov, 2018). It is thus deduced that the strong side of Russian-Central Asian relations lies in the similar authoritarian nature of their political regimes. Russian and Central Asian leaders feel an almost genetic closeness and share an understanding of what constitutes the best kind of political model while maintaining a common belief that Western democracy is not suitable for them. Therefore, for Central Asian leaders, cooperation with Russia is more suitable as they share similar backgrounds and political systems and Russia supports the continuity of authoritarianism in the region

which still shapes the political systems of all the republics. Russia's intent is further established through various intergovernmental organizations such as the CIS and EAEU³. Though many academics have played down the effectiveness of these organizations, I stress that they are part of Russia's key platforms of influence. Members of the organizations enjoy close relations with Russia and all have retained similar political and economic systems since independence, except for Georgia and Ukraine. The two countries have been part of the US backed GUAM⁴, which was created in balance to the CIS, and as a result have chosen Western development models, unveiling that they have moved away from Russia's sphere of influence. Their new leaders had voiced direct opposition to Russian 'imperialism' and preferred Western liberalization (Nixey, 2013). Contrastingly, in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, where there have been power transitions in recent times, it is observable that the core of their political systems remains the same with no real oppositional parties allowed to run⁵. The recent power transition in Uzbekistan has demonstrated the possibility of a new form of governance in the region. President Mirziyoyev advanced many positive economic and political reforms, improved relations with neighboring countries and joined other, wider intergovernmental organizations such as the Turkic Council and became an observer member of the WTO (Patnaik, 2019; Blackwood, 2020). As a result, this invited more support from the West but it seems that this support is limited to technical assistance in policy and institutional reforms; and genuine investments are predisposed for Russia and China. Recently, Russia has invested in the field of energy and an atomic plant in Uzbekistan. The latter, very recently officially joined the EAEU as an observer member⁶, emphasizing Russia's role in Uzbekistan's modernization initiatives.

³ Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU)

⁴ GUAM Organization for Democracy and Economic Development

⁵ *"The 2019 parliamentary elections in Uzbekistan took place under improved legislation and with greater tolerance of independent voices but did not yet demonstrate genuine competition and full respect of election day procedures"* (OSCE, 2020)

⁶ *"the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan approved the decision to apply for observer status with the Russian-led Eurasian Economic Union"* (Hashimova, 2020)

China and Central Asia

From a Chinese perspective, the most important reason for its presence in the region appears to be an effort to establish close ties with Central Asia in order to secure market access and the growing need for oil and natural gas. Since 1991, China has increased economic interests towards the region. To support this, the SCO was founded in 1995 and is the most active organization in the region today (Marketos, 2008).

At present, China views Central Asia as an economically integrated entity which will help to advance the Chinese global agenda and serve its energy needs. China's economic engine is so large that it requires vast volumes of energy (Marketos, 2008). Therefore, China's aim in the region is to make it one of the diversified energy sources and a regional economic partner. Through the BRI⁷, China has been able to boost intra-regional trade and became the region's main economic partner, overtaking Russia (Mariani, 2013).

However, it is clear that China is not able to exclusively dominate the region. It is important to point out that Russia is the most important military power in the region and could be so for years to come⁸. At the same time, claims that China has hidden motives in Central Asia aimed at dominance of the region are exaggerated. Politically, in comparison with Russia, China has neither the capacity nor the intention to be Central Asia's hegemon (Mariani, 2013). However, what is important to point out is that Russian and Chinese close cooperation in the SCO is clearly a move to prevent Western influence in the region. Nonetheless, Chinese investments are viewed positively by Central Asian leaders and even the Uyghur situation seems to have little effect for the continuation of cooperation.⁹

⁷ Belt and Road Initiative

⁸ 201st Motorized Rifle Division in Tajikistan and Manas Airbase in Kyrgyzstan

⁹ *"For [these governments], all of this is a matter of economics"* (Mirovalev, 2020)

Conclusion

It is evident that Russia's influence is dangerous for Central Asian integration as it feels the need to be involved in any such incentive. True, Russia retains a relatively central place in the politics of the Central Asian countries. But it does not represent an ideal for these countries and is not the model they would choose to emulate as they strive to achieve success in everything from economic reform to developing civil and cultural value systems. As Russia backs authoritarian regimes, a Central Asian Union made up of solely states from that region seems unlikely as Russia continuously attempts to force Central Asian countries separately into its sphere of influence.

At the same time, while being members of different wider regional organizations, the states are further differentiated in their interests which constitutes a threat for integration. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and more recently Uzbekistan, have been involved in many wider regional initiatives and are all members of the Turkic Council. Tajikistan's cooperativeness has been mostly in the sphere of security and by being left out of the Turkic Council for having an Iranian population, it is likely to search for a wider cooperation with Iran. Turkmenistan's isolationist foreign policy further blocks any inner regional initiatives. Overall, being part of different, wider organizations, Central Asian countries are 'entrapped' as none of these organizations are initiated by them. At the same time, this has caused the emergence of different national strategies as well as economic partners which continue to pull the countries apart from each other.

Finally, as China continues to cooperate with all the Central Asian states, there is a chance for regional cooperation to increase as a result of economic development. However, as long as China and Russia continue to form a duopoly in the region, Western ideas of democracy and economic liberalization are likely to be left out.

CONCLUSION

Almost three decades of existence of modern Central Asia proved that authoritarianism fueled by informal practices and external influence has an overarching impact for political and socio-economic development of Central Asian states and is the main constraint for their integration. It is observed that neopatrimonialism along with nepotism is the root cause of continued authoritarian regimes in Central Asia which impedes democratization and regionalism. In addition, spatial distribution of natural resources, different economic strategies and experiences of the republics further contributes to disintegration. Since regionalism is interlinked with liberalization, economic integration was further prevented because of the neopatrimonial nature of the republics which favors internal control and informal wealth accumulation from state resources. At the same time, the distinct economic experiences have caused regional tensions based on a conflict of interests. The water sharing issue exacerbated the existing economic hardships of the region, exposing the dangers of aggressive foreign policy. Externally, Russia's influence and backing of authoritarian regimes in Central Asia prevent them from uniting both politically and economically. On the opposite, Chinese economic interests in the region could trigger economic integration as the first step towards a Central Asian Union. However this seems impossible without genuine Western support towards democratization and liberalization of Central Asian countries.

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